

BRAND WP6.2 - Primary Focus Feed

Results for RadioNet Report

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Introduction

0.1 Scope

This document is a summary of the goals, challenges, design and manufacturing of the unique feed antenna designed at Onsala Space Observatory for the RadioNet project BRoad-bAND (BRAND) EVN. In this report it will be referenced as the "BRAND feed". The goal of this work was to include over a decade in frequency bandwidth for continuous observational coverage with one single wideband (broadband) feed. The frequency band of interest is 1.5–15.5 GHz. This is "10.3 to 1" in fractional bandwidth, also written as 10.3:1, which indicates the highest operational frequency is 10.3 times larger than the lowest. The first feed prototype was tailor-designed for the prime-focus configuration on the 100 m Effelsberg telescope $f/D=0.3$, half-opening (half-subtended) angle: $\theta_0=79.6^\circ$.

0.2 Choosing Technology

In the early phase of this work a pre-study was performed of existing technologies with potential to extend the bandwidth to over 10:1 from previous state of the art fractional bandwidths of 6:1 and 7:1. Several wideband technologies were investigated such as the eleven feed and new developments of coaxial feeds. Finally, the decision was made to go for the Quad-Ridge Flared Horn (QRFH) due to the robust design, low-loss structure, matured technology, phase center consistency, low-cost manufacture, and a well-known optimization scheme for this type of project.

0.3 Quad-Ridge Flared Horn (QRFH)

The all-metal Quad-Ridge Flared Horn (QRFH) was a good starting point for extending the bandwidth to 10.3:1 (1.5–15.5 GHz) - since it is a well known and robust feed concept. The QRFH have intrinsically low loss in its standard form and the feeding can be done with either two single-ended 50Ω ports or differential four-port structure. The simplicity of the single-ended approach is attractive also because the use of only two low-noise amplifiers (LNA) in total. The QRFH technology has been successfully applied for radio astronomy and wideband applications for many years - typically used for frequency bandwidths of 3:1 to 7:1 and reflectors with $f/D=0.4$ to 0.6. With an increasing bandwidth the challenge is to keep the beamwidth relatively constant over frequency to achieve a good illumination of the telescope surface. For the QRFH typically beamwidth decreases with increasing frequency in a wideband feed. The QRFH is a waveguide type horn - meaning it has a distinct lower-end cut-off frequency and can be designed as both rectangular and circular. The sharp cut-off is beneficial because it works as a natural high-pass filter for RFI outside the lower end of the band. The input-reflection of the QRFH can generally be designed to better than $S_{11} < -10$ dB across the band after optimization, which is a common target limit in the community of wideband feed design.

0.4 Main Design Goals

The main design goals of the projects can be summarized as:

1. Achieve an average aperture efficiency better than 50 % across the frequency band 1.5–15.5 GHz for an $f/D=0.3$ reflector.

2. Achieve an input-reflection less than -10 dB across the frequency band 1.5–15.5 GHz.
3. Modify the existing QRFH technology to a minimum - for smooth integration with existing component-technology in the analogue receiver chain.

0.5 Main Challenges

The main challenges of the projects can be summarized as:

1. Achieve a more stable beamwidth over frequency.
2. Illuminate a deep reflector as the Effelsberg $f/D=0.3$.
3. Matching a 10:1 bandwidth in impedance.
4. Keep the QRFH technology close to its original and well appreciated form.

To achieve this we needed to introduce a novel concept in the QRFH design, and perform detailed and rigorous optimization for optimal performance.

0.6 Published Work

The work to develop the BRAND feed has led to international peer-reviewed publications and community interest due to the novel work presented [1]–[7]. For detailed technical information on the primary-focus antenna feed - the design, manufacture and testing is largely presented in its entirety in:

[1] J. Flygare, M. Pantaleev, and S. Olvhammar, "BRAND: Ultra-Wideband Feed Development for the European VLBI Network - A Dielectrically Loaded Decade Bandwidth Quad-Ridge Flared Horn," in *Proceedings of 12th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP2018)*, London, UK, 9-13 April 2018. (Peer-reviewed).

Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8568495>

[2] J. Flygare and M. Pantaleev, "Dielectrically Loaded Quad-Ridge Flared Horn for Beamwidth Control over Decade Bandwidth - Optimization, Manufacture, and Measurement," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 207–216, 2020. (Peer-reviewed).

Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8852836>

These publications ([1], [2]) should be seen as complimentary documents throughout this report and are referenced for further detail.

0.7 Brief Description of Key Results

We have shown that by using a low-loss low-profile dielectric load insert in the QRFH metal structure, while keeping the rest of the technology unchanged, we can extend the frequency range up to (and further than) 10:1 bandwidth - covering the whole BRAND frequency range of 1.5–15.5 GHz with one QRFH feed. The technique we developed through this work has been recognized for its novelty in the well renown journal of IEEE Transactions of Antennas and Propagation in publication [2] mentioned above. The main benefit of the dielectric is to help maintain a near constant beamwidth over such a large bandwidth for the QRFH to illuminate the telescope properly. It also helps

in achieving low input-reflection at the feed output. The feed is designed for an input reflection less than -10 dB over the full bandwidth with an average aperture efficiency better than 50 % across the band. The astronomy figure-of-merit - sensitivity or System Equivalent Flux Density (SEFD) - is estimated for an elevation of 45° to be in the range of 25–45 Jy over the frequency band - this is comparable to current narrowband receivers according to available data from Effelsberg. Due to the ultra wideband (UWB) frequency range and large half-opening angle of Effelsberg, these results should be considered very good. The BRAND feed has been designed, manufactured and measured with satisfying results and the prototype can be seen in Fig. 1. The BRAND feed was designed during 2017-2018 with prototype manufacture and testing during the second half of 2018. In November 2019 the BRAND feed prototype was shipped to Max Planck Institute for Radio Astronomy in Bonn, Germany to await integration in the receiver dewar for future tests on the Effelsberg 100 m telescope.

Fig. 1: (a) Manufactured prototype of the BRAND feed, here shown in the lab during S-parameter tests. (b) The dielectric load can be seen at the center of the feed in white.

1 Dielectrically Loaded Quad-Ridge Flared Horn

The goal of the feed is to collect the incoming radiation focused at the focal point of the reflector telescope. It is the first component in the analogue receiver chain. The BRAND project will cover a very large bandwidth over the frequency range 1.5–15.5 GHz which allows for both science at many frequencies, but also an increased UV coverage in Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI). Due to the very large collecting area of the Effelsberg 100 m, the sensitivity of the observations are very high and is therefore a very good selection for the first BRAND demonstrator. The QRFH technology has been heavily explored for reflectors with half-opening angles of $\theta_0=45^\circ-65^\circ$ and so therefore the Effelsberg large half-opening angle of $\theta_0 = 79.6^\circ$ presented an interesting challenge. The half-opening angle is counted from the focal point center-line of the reflector to the edge of the reflector, illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: (a) The 100 m Effelsberg telescope. (b) An illustration of half-opening angle, $\theta_0 = 79.6^\circ$ for Effelsberg (feed size is highly exaggerated for illustration)

1.1 Design

The feed is an aluminum metal structure of a flared quad-ridge waveguide, where the ridge-technology makes the feed more compact and wideband - compared to other horn-type antennas. The ridges create intrinsically a dual-linearly polarized feed with two single-ended output ports connecting to corresponding LNAs. The polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE or “Teflon”) dielectric load, Fig. 4(a), inserted in the center of the QRFH improves beamwidth control over the decade frequency band with low loss-contribution. The BRAND feed measures 87 mm in height and 292 mm in diameter at the aperture. The ridges are 2 mm thick and the dielectric load is 52.5 mm in total height with a maximum diameter of 7.5 mm. The shape of the horn and the ridges are optimized from exponential functions and the dielectric load is based on geometric shapes combined. The metal and dielectric structures are manufactured using computer controlled numerical (CNC) machining. For the first BRAND feed prototype the outer structure (not impacting the performance) of the horn was shaped with electrostatic discharge machining (EDM). These techniques are well established and commercially available for low-cost manufacturing. The CNC-made ridges are clamped between the four horn pieces for good electrical contact, as seen in Fig. 4(b). Detailed description of design and optimization procedures for the BRAND feed are found in [1] and [2]. A tolerance analysis to achieve nominal performance in a manufactured feed is available in [2]. The first prototype is shown in perspective view Fig. 1 with the dielectric load enlarged. Some of the detailed parts that was manufactured are highlighted in Fig. 4, Fig. 7, and Fig. 8. For more pictures see [2].

1.2 Mechanical Design: Slim

Due to the small dimensions present in the throat section of the BRAND feed, several mechanical design modifications have been considered to make the feed easier to manufacture. In Fig. 3 an overview picture is presented of the simple model used for fast optimization (left) and the mechanical model that was manufactured (right). The most important difference is the cut in the bottom section, illustrated in Fig. 5, to reduce the length of the drilled hole through the ridges. It also simplifies the mounting of the horn. Figure 3 show that solid material was added around the feed to make it more robust. Control-simulations were continuously used during the conversion from simulation model to mechanical model - this to make sure no degradation in electromagnetic performance would occur. Due to the modification of the feeding-section, some added design features

Fig. 3: (a) Simple feed model used for fast optimization. (b) Optimized model transferred into mechanical structure for manufacturing.

Fig. 4: (a) Zoom-in on a 2mm-thick ridge clamped between horn pieces. (b) Manufactured dielectric load. (c) Push-chuck and clamping mechanism for feed-pin contact. (d) Zoom-in between ridges (without dielectric load installed).

increased the isolation between polarizations which was desired. This is especially good since isolation usually degrades to some extent when the feed is manufactured due to small misalignments and tolerance errors in the feed-pin placement.

Fig. 5: The mechanical concept of the BRAND feed with a "slim" bottom section to make the feeding point easier to manufacture with high precision.

1.3 Single-Ended Feeding

To reduce manufacturing costs and complexity, the SMA connectors and wire pins at the feeding point are commercially available standard microwave products, see Fig. 7. The SMA-connector is connected to a "peeled" UT-047 semi-rigid used as a launch pin (or feeding pin). The feeding pin enters through one ridge and terminates in the opposing ridge, where it is clamped with a push-screw connection, see Fig. 6.

The locking mechanism and clamping structure were made in-house in a mechanical lathe at the Onsala mechanical workshop, presented in Fig. 4(c) and Fig. 8. Exploration into differential feeding was done early on in the design-stages but did not give an improved performance for this bandwidth and was therefore discarded in favor of the 50Ω single-ended standard solution.

1.4 Key Results

The QRFH design show simulated aperture efficiency average 50.6 % for both polarizations on reflector ($f/D=0.3$), see Fig. 9(a), which should be considered a very good result for such a broad band. This is an improvement of previous very-low gain QRFHs for prime-focus. We see in Fig. 9(a) that by loading the QRFH design with dielectric (PTFE) we improve the aperture efficiency from mid to high frequency band substantially. The black curve is the aperture efficiency, η_a , and the green is phase efficiency, η_{ph}

Fig. 6: Illustration of the feed pin connection between two opposite ridges.

. The aim for a constant high phase efficiency is important to keep the total aperture efficiency high. This is of course related to how the feed is mounted relative the focal point of the Effelsberg antenna. In these simulations, the feed is placed such that the reflector geometrical focal point is 36.5 mm inside the horn measured from the horn aperture. It is also clear that the reduction of performance at higher frequency is because of a sloping illumination efficiency η_{ill} which decreases the overall efficiency (under-illumination of the dish). Because of the dielectric load however, the decrease in illumination efficiency is strongly reduced (light blue curve) which gives a good overall aperture efficiency.

In Table 1 all five sub-efficiencies and the total product of these (aperture efficiency) are displayed as averages over the frequency band 1.5–15.5 GHz in a $f/D=0.3$ reflector (Effelsberg). The efficiency averages are shown for the BRAND feed without and with the dielectric load installed. Because of the dielectric load the total improvement in aperture efficiency average is 9.1 %. The improvement in polarization efficiency can also be displayed in the form of intrinsic cross-polarization ratio (IXR) without and with dielectric load, Fig. 9(b). The dielectric load is clearly improving the mid to high frequencies of the band, while the horn shape dominates the lower frequencies.

Table 1: Simulated average efficiencies for the BRAND feed in $f/D=0.3$ reflector.

	η_{ill}	η_{sp}	η_{BOR1}	η_{pol}	η_{ph}	η_a
without Diel. Load, 1.5–15.5 GHz	62.5	96.4	86.3	86.6	92.5	41.5
with Diel. Load, 1.5–15.5 GHz	68.8	96.3	87.7	90.8	96.6	50.6

To estimate the observational sensitivity figure-of-merit we calculate the system noise temperature, T_{sys} . We assume all spill-over from the feed is hitting the hot ground which is set to an equivalent brightness temperature of $T_g=290$ K. This assumption is an overestimation especially for lower elevations where more spill-over could be terminated on the sky. The spill-over contribution is the strongest at the low-frequency part of the band and reduces for higher frequencies due to lower illumination beyond the reflector edge. Calculations of antenna noise temperature, T_a , and system noise temperature are based on Eq. (1), where η_{sp} is the spill-over efficiency, T_{phy} , physical temperature of the feed, T_{sky} is the sky brightness temperature, and η_{rad} is the radiation efficiency. The receiver noise temperature, T_{rec} , is estimated to be 18–25 K over the band in total

Fig. 7: SMA-connector interface fed with a "peeled" semi-rigid UT-047 as launch pin, 0.94 mm Teflon (PTFE), 0.287 mm SPCW pin. This follows the dimensions assumed for the feeding during simulations. Connectors are specified up to 27 GHz with two-hole mounting, center-hole has a maximum 0.3 mm acceptance diameter.

from measured LNA data and other receiver components. The estimated system noise temperature is between 35 K and 63 K over the frequency band. A detailed breakdown

Fig. 8: Lathed push-screw fixture made to connect the feed pin in the opposite ridge.

of the system noise contributions are presented in [2].

$$\begin{aligned} T_a &= \eta_{\text{sp}} T_{\text{sky}} + (1 - \eta_{\text{sp}}) T_g \\ T_{\text{sys}} &= \eta_{\text{rad}} T_a + (1 - \eta_{\text{rad}}) T_{\text{phy}} + T_{\text{rec}} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The observational sensitivity is here expressed as System Equivalent Flux Density (SEFD) which is calculated according to Eq. (2). A lower number of SEFD indicates a more sensitive (better) telescope. Here the effective aperture, A_{eff} , is proportional to the physical area of the reflector, A_{phy} , and the product of the radiation efficiency, η_{rad} , and the aperture efficiency η_a which emphasizes the importance of the feed design. The constant k_B is the Boltzmann constant.

$$\begin{aligned} A_{\text{eff}} &= \eta_{\text{rad}} \eta_a A_{\text{phy}} \\ \text{SEFD} &= 2k_B (T_{\text{sys}} / A_{\text{eff}}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The estimated SEFD for the BRAND feed on Effelsberg is presented in Fig. 10. Blockage is included in the estimation. The result shows a SEFD between 25–45 Jy for

Fig. 9: (a) Improvement in phase efficiency (green), illumination efficiency (blue), aperture efficiency (black) due to the dielectric load presented (solid curve is the feed with dielectric load, dash curve is without). (b) Corresponding improvement in intrinsic cross-polarization ratio (IXR) on-dish. Results are simulations $f/D=0.3$ reflector (Effelsberg).

a telescope elevation of 45° which is comparable to current narrowband receiver systems according to Effelsberg data. The increase of SEFD at the lower frequencies is a result of increased spill-over noise and reduced polarization performance in the total efficiency. The increase at the high frequencies is the result of slight reduction in total aperture efficiency.

Fig. 10: SEFD estimation on 100 m prime-focus configuration of $f/D=0.3$ for elevation angle 45° .

1.5 Dielectric Load Shrinkage Simulation

To implement the the dielectric load in the design, emphasis was put on a tight fit in-between the ridges so it will not deviate from boresight in alignment. The bottom cylinder also ensures that it is stabilized and held in place from the pressure of the back-

plate, and clamped in the backshort, this restricts the dielectric load to move when the feed is rotated. The feed pins also guarantee that it can not slide out, however this is not an acceptable solution on its own. The bottom cylinder also helps with thermal contact to the metal of the feed in addition to its connection to the four ridges. From thermal data of several sources of PTFE (data in: http://www.rjchase.com/ptfe_handbook.pdf), and previous dewar-cooling cycles in our laboratory, it was estimated that a worst-case scenario of shrinkage (from room temperature) would be 3-4 % at 20 K temperature. For 70 K, which is the feed stage temperature in the dewar, a worst-case scenario of shrinkage was estimated to 2-3 %. Within this specification, the dielectric load was designed so that it would not be able to “fall out” even if a 7 % shrinkage occurred. At 7 % uniform shrinkage simulations started showing a significant negative effect on the radiation pattern. The bottom cylinder support is made large enough so the piece cannot slide through the ridges, even at 7 % shrinkage. The hole for the feed pins in the dielectric load was deliberately made bigger than necessary so that even a shrinkage of 7 %, would not crush the pins together mechanically. The aluminum shrinkage is assumed 0 % when calculating these scenarios. The realistic case is that the aluminum could shrink with at most a factor 1/5 to that of the PTFE. From experience with all-aluminum QRFHs in cryogenic dewars up to 18 GHz any shrinkage has been small in terms of the measured feed performance. If the alignment mechanism from the cylinder would falter during cryogenic operations, a backup solution of a small hole with a guiding screw-pin (made from PTFE) fastened through the backplate of the horn could be implemented to keep the dielectric aligned, Fig. 11.

Fig. 11: Potential improvement to alignment of the dielectric load.

1.6 Beam Pattern Measurements in Anechoic Chamber

Fig. 12: (a) Mounting of the feed. (b) Front-facing view.

Fig. 13: Backplate of the BRAND feed, threaded holes indicated by arrows. SMA-connectors for the two ports are seen in gold.

The measurement of the feed beam pattern was performed in an anechoic chamber specified for farfield measurements, Fig. 12. The BRAND feed backplate is equipped with both threaded holes (red arrows) and through-holes for mounting both during measurement and in cryogenic dewar, Fig. 13. The pattern was measured in steps of 5° in ϕ (azimuth) and 1° in θ over the full sphere, sampled each 0.5 GHz. The simulated and measured beam patterns are in good agreement over the frequency band, with some discrepancies over 1.5–2 GHz. This is because the transmit antenna reference (ETS-Lindgren’s Model 3164-05) and measurement chamber was unspecified over 1.5–2 GHz range, but still usable according to the suppliers specification. The desired widening of the beam in the upper frequency range due to the dielectric was confirmed with

measurements, illustrated in Fig. 14 for 15.5 GHz. In Fig. 15 the agreement between simulated and measured patterns is presented as 3D-patterns for a set of frequencies 1.5, 5.0, 8.5, 12.0, and 15.5 GHz. The "seam" seen in the middle of the measured pattern is a visual effect as the measured pattern is put together as measured "slices" of the total pattern. The slight rotational difference between simulated and measured seen in the top-view is another visual effect from the plotting coordinate's alignment.

Fig. 14: Simulated and measured beam pattern in H-plane at 15.5 GHz to exemplify the widening effect of the beam due to the dielectric. The figure to the right illustrates (crudely) how the widening of the beam improves the reflector illumination.

Fig. 15: Simulated (column 1 and 3) and measured (column 2 and 4) beam pattern in 3D, normalized to 0 dB, for 1.5 GHz (row 1), 5.0 GHz (row 2), 8.5 GHz (row 3), 12.0 GHz (row 4), and 15.5 GHz (row 5). Columns 1 and 2 show the perspective view, while 3 and 4 show the top view.

1.7 S-parameter Measurement

Fig. 16: BRAND feed during S-parameter measurement setup in the Onsala lab.

The S-parameters are measured with a calibrated Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) Agilent E8362C PNA specified over the frequency range 10 MHz to 20 GHz. Input-reflection and isolation was measured in the 2-port setup, see Fig. 16. The simulated input reflection (S_{11}, S_{22}) is less than -10 dB across the band, see Fig. 17(a), while the first measured prototype show a worst-case input reflection of -7 dB, Fig. 17(b). The degradation is due to small errors in the feed throat section at the launch pins. The measured S-parameters are acceptable to be used in the prototype receiver. In [2] the tolerances are derived and analyzed, and intervals for acceptable manufacturing errors are derived for future feed production to obtain nominal performance across the band. These discrepancies have very little effect on the radiation performance and beam patterns. The isolation is measured to around 35 dB between the ports which is an expected and acceptable number for manufactured QRFHs. The effect of the dielectric load on the impedance matching is visible in Fig. 17. For the lower frequencies the cut-off is clearly "sharper" with the dielectric load installed.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 17: S-parameters without and with the dielectric load. (a) Simulated. (b) Measured.

2 Short Notes

2.1 VGOS Compability

The BRAND project includes the overlap of VGOS frequencies in the design objectives. Therefore evaluating the BRAND feed in the VGOS geometry is relevant. In [5]-[6] this comparison is presented together with other recent feed package designs.

2.2 Tolerance Analysis

For future production of BRAND feed a tolerance analysis was provided to the crucial throat/feeding section of the dielectrically loaded QRFH, this is detailed on p.213–215 in [2]. Tolerance intervals are provided to achieve nominal performance.

2.3 Additional Results

On p.210–211 in [2] more measured results and lab-setup regarding beam pattern, beamwidth and gain is presented.

References

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